

TOWARDS A FATIGUE LOAD MODEL FOR COMPOSITE ROAD BRIDGES

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ABSTRACT

The current fatigue load models (FLMs) for road bridges were calibrated based on steel and reinforced concrete bridges. They are not applicable to fiber-polymer composite bridges mainly because the damage rate, i.e., the slope of the fatigue load versus life ($F-N$) curve of composites is flatter than that of steel and concrete. A double-axle FLM was proposed for composite bridges and calibrated using a composite road bridge. Three different slopes of the $F-N$ curve were assumed, all representative for composites, and a series of real traffic loads from three countries were used for the calibration. The FLM was calibrated based on the equivalent damage between the real traffic loads and the proposed FLM.

KEYWORDS

Composite bridges; Fatigue load model; Fatigue load life ($F-N$) curve; Cycle count; Equivalent damage.

INTRODUCTION

The fatigue verification of road bridges due to traffic loads is based on fatigue load models (FLMs), as specified in EN 1991-2 (EN 1991-2, 2003), AASHTO LRFD (AASHTO, 2010) and Swiss Code (SIA 261) (SIA 261, 2003). These FLMs were calibrated to obtain (i) a stress range below the fatigue limit, resulting in infinite fatigue life, or (ii) similar damage as generated by actual traffic based on the concept of equivalent damage using the Palmgren-Miner law and the stress-fatigue life ($S-N$) curve. The classic power law relationship expressed in Eq.1 is commonly used to characterize $S-N$ curves for structural steel members (in the range between 10^4 cycles and 5×10^6 cycles), where the constant C and slope m are model parameters:

$$N = C \Delta\sigma^{-m} \tag{Eq. 1}$$

where N is the number of cycles to failure, C is a constant representing the influence of the structural detail, $\Delta\sigma$ is the constant amplitude stress range, and m is the slope coefficient of the fatigue load-life curve in a double-logarithmic scale.

Taking the calibration of FLMs in EN 1991-2 (EN 1991-2, 2003) as an example, the relevant $S-N$ curve with slope $m = 3$ or 5 was selected for steel bridges and traffic load measurements on Auxerre motorway, France, in 1986, were selected because they represented one of the heaviest loads in Europe at that time. Five different FLMs (FLM1 to FLM5) are defined in (EN 1991-2, 2003) for various purposes. FLM3, which incorporates a damage equivalent factor, is most commonly used to perform fatigue verifications. The model was calibrated by defining the damage produced by FLM3 at two million cycles equal to the accumulated damage generated by the real traffic over the design service life (100 years). Current investigations of FLMs focus mainly on the calibration of FLM3 regarding the damage equivalent factor (Croce, 2020; Maddah & Nussbaumer, 2014; Walbridge et al., 2013) and the development of a new FLM (Maljaars, 2020) due to the significant increase in heavy traffic loads in recent years and site-dependency of traffic in different countries.

Fiber-polymer composite decks have attracted attention in new construction or refurbishment of existing bridges due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent fatigue and corrosion resistance,

and low-cost transportation and construction (Keller et al., 2014; Keller & Gürtler, 2005). However, current FLMs cannot be applied for the fatigue verification of composite bridges, because the $S-N$ curve of composites is significantly flatter than that of steel, with the slope m varying from 10 to 20 (Liu et al., 2023; A. P. Vassilopoulos & Keller, 2015; Anastasios P. Vassilopoulos & Keller, 2011). The slope of the $S-N$ curve of composites depends on the material type, i.e., the composition of different types of fibers and polymers, and failure mechanisms in materials, joints and decks. However, a FLM for composite road bridges has not yet been developed. Thus, the present work aims to make a first step towards a FLM for composite road bridges.

METHODOLOGY OF CALIBRATION OF FLM

A methodology for the calibration of a FLM for composite road bridges was developed, which is based on the calibration of FLM3 for structural steels in (Nussbaumer et al., 2011). The process begins with the selection of a composite bridge and the identification of the critical location, where damage or failure may initiate. This identification is performed on the member or joint level according to (CEN/TC 250, 2022). The influence surface of the internal forces at this location are derived. The process is then divided into two parts. In part one, a series of real traffic loads is run across the influence surface to obtain the force (F) history and the corresponding spectrum is derived by performing a cycle count using the Rainflow method (Amzallag et al., 1994). Concerning the fatigue resistance, the slope of the $F-N$ curve can be determined from fatigue testing at the structural member or joint level for composite bridges, or assumed if testing is not carried out. The equivalent force range is obtained based on the equivalent damage using the $F-N$ curve and Miner rule. In part two the force range obtained from the FLM is obtained. Finally, the axle load of the FLM is determined by equating the force ranges resulting from the FLM to that generated by real traffic loads.

WIM DATABASES

Data selection

The traffic records used for calibrating the load model were obtained from weigh-in-motion (WIM) systems, which provide measurements of gross vehicle weights (GVW), axle weights (WA), number of axles, and axle spacings (SA) (Lydon et al., 2016). Representative traffic measurements from motorways of three European countries were selected for the calibration of the FLM, which varied in recorded years, periods during the years, and traffic volume. An overview of the WIM databases used is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of WIM databases per traffic direction (Croce, 2020; Maddah & Nussbaumer, 2012, 2014; Maljaars, 2020).

Country	Motor way	Direction	Duration (month)	Recording time	Per lane	Average daily traffic after filtering ^a	N_{obs} per year ^a
France	A6	Paris > Lyon	0.07 (2 days)	1986 (29-30, May)	Slow	3130	1.02×10^6
					Fast	220	-
The Netherlands	A16	Rotterdam > Moerdijk	1	2008 (Apr.)	Slow	6874	2.32×10^6
					Fast	1035	-
			10	2015 (Jan. - Oct.)	Slow	6102	2.06×10^6
					Fast	781	-
			1	2018 (Apr.)	Slow	6294	2.13×10^6
					Fast	924	-
Switzerland	A1	Oberburen > Zurich	192	2006 - 2021	Slow	1760	0.49×10^6
					Fast	148	-
	A2	Ceneri > Bellinzona	192	2006 - 2021	Slow	2187	0.68×10^6
					Fast	286	-
	A2	Gotthard > Wassen	264	1999 - 2021	Slow	1476	0.47×10^6

^a These values were obtained by extrapolating or averaging the recorded data.

The traffic records from the Motorway A6 in Auxerre, France, in 1986 were selected because they were previously used to calibrate the FLMs of Eurocode and contained heavy European continental traffic with the highest frequency of large axle weights recorded at that time. The motorway has three lanes for each traffic direction and the traffic of the slow and first fast lanes of one direction was recorded, in which the records during two days were considered as representative. The records from the motorway A16 near Moerdijk in the Netherlands, near the harbor of Rotterdam, were selected because they included a large number of heavy loads since the harbor is one of the largest harbors in Europe. Similarly, only the traffic of the slow and first fast lanes was recorded among three lanes in one traffic direction, with records spanning multiple periods in April 2008 and 2018, and from January to October 2015. The accuracy of the WIM database was verified with strain gauge measurements on the bridge structure, as reported in (Maljaars, 2020). The last group of traffic records was selected from the two most heavily used motorways in Switzerland, and the measurements were continuously recorded for varying periods of 16 to 22 years. The records were collected from a section of the A1 motorway near Zurich, including both slow and fast lanes in one direction from Oberbüren to Zurich. The measurements from two sections of the A2 motorway were selected: one was near Monte Ceneri where both slow and fast lanes were recorded from the direction of Monte Ceneri to Bellinzona, and the other one was near Gotthard where only one lane was recorded from Gotthard to Wassen.

Filtering conditions

Traffic databases obtained from WIM measurements must be examined and filtered before they can be used for calibration since they may contain incorrect or inaccurate data, as reported in (Wassef et al., 2014). The vehicle gross weight or axle weight is limited to 50 t and 12 t in most European countries (Wassef et al., 2014), respectively. However, the permissible values in this study are increased to 100 t and 25 t to take into account certain special permissions and illegal heavy vehicles. The minimum axle spacing, for instance, cannot significantly fall below 0.6 m based on the vehicle geometry. Light vehicles with a total GVW less than 35 kN or WA less than 8.8 kN can furthermore be excluded in the calibration because they do not significantly contribute to the cumulative damage (Croce, 2020; Nussbaumer et al., 2011). Thus, the traffic raw data measurements were filtered based on the following three criteria:

- 1) $35 \text{ kN} < \text{GVW} < 1000 \text{ kN}$;
- 2) $8.8 \text{ kN} < \text{WA} < 250 \text{ kN}$;
- 3) $\text{SA} > 0.6 \text{ m}$.

The number of average daily traffic after filtering was counted for all motorways, as listed in Table 1, and the accuracy of the databases and filtering criteria were validated by comparing them to those in (Croce, 2020; Maljaars, 2020). The traffic category on a bridge can be defined based on the number of heavy vehicles, N_{obs} , ($\text{GVW} > 100 \text{ kN}$) per year and per slow lane, as specified in [1] (Table 4.5). Thus, the traffic categories in Auxerre (France), Moerdijk (the Netherlands) and Switzerland were determined to be category 2 ($N_{\text{obs}} > 0.5 \times 10^6$, roads and motorways with medium flow rates of lorries), category 1 ($N_{\text{obs}} > 2.0 \times 10^6$, roads and motorways with 2 or more lanes per direction with high flow rates of lorries), and category 2, respectively, based on N_{obs} , as listed in Table 1.

PROPOSED FLM

Figure 1: Proposed FLM for composite structures ($Q = \text{axel load}$).

A double-axle system is proposed to represent the FLM with an axle load of Q and axle spacing of 1.2 m, as shown in Figure 1, similarly as specified for FLM3 in EN 1991-2 and in Swiss standard SIA261. The selected axle spacing is close to the most frequency occurring axle spacing (1.25 m), which might be corresponding to the axle spacing of the tandem- or tridem-axle group for vehicles, which was observed in the traffic records. This simple FLM is also justified by the fact that the spans of composite slab bridges or composite bridge decks on steel girders are comparably small, i.e., rarely exceeding 10-15 m.

CALIBRATION OF FLM

Composite bridge

Identification of critical locations

The two-lane Avançon Bridge, built in 2012 in Switzerland, was selected for the calibration of the FLM. The 11.45 m span bridge is composed of a composite sandwich deck slab adhesively bonded onto two steel main girders (Keller et al., 2014). The design service life is 100 years. A simplified plan view of the bridge is shown in Figure 2, which neglects the skew angles of 65° ; they were not considered in the calibration since they do not affect the results. The composite deck, which spans over 7.50 m in the transverse direction, consists of three similarly sized sandwich panels, which are connected using adhesively bonded Z-shaped joints, i.e., butt joints in the core and scarf joints in the face sheets. Each sandwich panel has a thickness of 285 mm and is composed of two 22-mm-thick glass composite face sheets and a 241-mm-thick balsa wood core which provides shear resistance for the panel. More information on the fiber architecture and mechanical properties of the composite components can be found in (Keller et al., 2014).

Figure 2. Simplified plan view of two-lane Avançon bridge (excluding skew angles), with dimensions of experimental beam under four-point loading across one joint, and FLM.

To verify the design of the transverse panel-to-panel adhesive joints, four-point bending experiments on full-scale beams were performed with the general setup indicated in Figure 2. The beam dimensions were 4.85 m in length, 0.6 m in width, and with the same depth as the bridge deck. The adhesive joint was arranged orthogonally to the beam axis at mid-span. The load versus deflection response in mid-span exhibited an almost linear behavior, with the ultimate failure load reaching 190 kN per loading point, when a fiber-tear failure occurred in the face sheet laminates (Keller et al., 2014). Assuming that this joint is also the critical component concerning fatigue, the calibration of the FLM was performed at this location.

Moment vs. number of cycles curve

The static bending moment resistance of the joint (460 kN·m/m) was determined to be the critical sectional resistance rather than the shear resistance because the shear force reached only 54% of the shear resistance of the balsa core at beam failure (Keller et al., 2014). Taking the moment resistance as an average value, the characteristic value (5% fractile) was estimated (320 kN·m/m) by assuming a coefficient of variation of 15% based on EN 1990 (EN 1990, 2001). The design value for fatigue resistance was then derived to be 160 kNm/m by dividing by the partial factor of $\gamma_{Mf} = 2.0$, as specified in (CEN/TC 250, 2022). Previous studies (Jiang et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021) have suggested that parameter C in equation (1) corresponds to the static resistance, i.e. to half of a cycle of a “fatigue” experiment. Three representative values for m were assumed, namely, $m = 10, 15$ and 20 . Thus, the $M-N$ curves could be determined for the composite bridge with different slopes, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: $M-N$ curves of a composite bridge with different slopes.

Influence surface

As derived above, the transverse adhesive deck joint was identified as the critical location for the fatigue resistance, and the maximum response was identified to occur in the middle of the transverse joint area, i.e., point “A” (Figure 2). The traffic was assumed to run on one lane of the bridge, with its center on the steel girder, as shown for the FLM in Figure 2. To obtain the influence surface of the bending moment of point “A” in span direction, a bridge model was developed using SAP 2000 software and taking the orthotropy of the composite face sheets into account. The resulting influence surface of point “A” is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Influence surface of bending moment in span direction for critical point “A” (transverse adhesive joint at mid-width).

Cycle count

The moment responses at point “A” were obtained by running the recorded axle weights with corresponding axle spacings of each vehicle across the influence surface in the center of one lane, which resulted in a series of variable bending moment histories. A representative moment response of point “A” generated by the traffic records on the Auxerre motorway is shown in Figure 5. The Rainflow

method was then used for cycle counting to generate the moment range spectrum, which converted variable moments into an equivalent set of constant amplitude moments with their respective number of cycles. A MATLAB program was developed to perform this calculation.

Figure 5: A representative moment response history at point “A” generated by a series of traffic records from Auxerre motorway.

The moment spectrum obtained from the Auxerre motorway records, i.e. the number of cycles, n_i , versus the moment range, ΔM_i , is shown in Figure 6. It should be noted that the cycle count results were established for one year, which was extrapolated by replicating the daily results. The moment range varied from 0.3 to 11 kN·m/m, and the spectrum distribution generally represented that of the axle weights because higher axle weights resulted in higher moment responses. The distributions exhibited a significant decreasing trend with an increasing moment range because the large axle weights were less frequent.

Figure 6: Moment range versus number of cycles from traffic records per year from Auxerre motorway records.

Establishment of FLM

The equivalent moment range ($\Delta M_{eq, real}$) at two million cycles, generated by the real traffic records over the design service life of 100 years, was calculated using Eq. 2, based on the rule of equivalent damage.

$$\Delta M_{eq, real} = \left[\frac{\sum n_i \cdot (\Delta M_i)^m}{2 \times 10^6} \right]^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The moment range ($\Delta M_{eq, FLM}$) from the FLM was expressed as a function of the axle load (Q), which was obtained from running the FLM across the influence surface. The axle load Q of the FLM was determined by equating $\Delta M_{eq, real} = \Delta M_{eq, FLM}$. The cycle count obtained from real traffic records over the design service life was extrapolated by linearly replicating daily records on the Auxerre motorway, monthly records on the Moerdijk motorway and annual records in Switzerland. Thus, the axle load Q of the FLM derived from different motorways and years is shown in Figure 7 for the three slopes of $M-N$ curves.

Figure 7: Axle load of FLM obtained from annual traffic records in France (Auxerre), the Netherlands (Moerdijk) and Switzerland for slopes of $m = 10, 15$ and 20 of $M-N$ curves.

The average axle loads of the FLM for the different slopes was determined as 102.5 kN, 103.2 kN and 109.0 kN, respectively, and exhibited an approximately linear increase with an increase in the slope of $M-N$ curves, as fitted in Figure 7. The characteristic values (i.e., 95% fractiles) of the axle load were then determined to be 115 kN, 117 kN and 124 kN for slopes of $m = 10, 15$ and 20 , respectively, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Characteristic values of axle loads of proposed FLM for slopes of $m = 10, 15$ and 20 .

CONCLUSIONS

A double-axle fatigue model is proposed for composite bridges and was calibrated using an existing composite road bridge and experimental full-scale data. Three different slopes of $m = 10, 15$ and 20 of the $M-N$ curves were assumed and a series of real traffic loads from France, the Netherlands and Switzerland was used to calibrate the model. The transverse adhesive deck joint was identified as the critical location in the composite bridge for the fatigue resistance. Cycle counting was performed based on the moment responses at this critical location, which were obtained from running the recorded traffic across the influence surface at the critical location. This calibration was performed by defining the accumulative damage produced by the FLM at two million cycles equal to that generated by the real traffic over the design service life. The characteristic values of the axle loads of the FLM were determined to be 115 kN, 117 kN and 124 kN for slopes of $m = 10, 15$ and 20 , respectively. The values exhibited a linear increase with an increase of the slopes of the $M-N$ curves. To further validate the proposed FLM, two other composite bridges have been selected and the FLM calibration is in progress.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon request.